

POTENTIAL MULTIPURPOSE TREES (MPTS) FOR ENHANCING AGROFORESTRY PRODUCTION IN SOUTH INDIA: SPECIES, SILVICULTURE MANAGEMENT AND SUCCESSFUL MODELS

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Abstract

As we know, agroforestry is a beautiful combination of agriculture and forestry for enhancing production (food and wood) as well as protecting our environment. From time immemorial, farmers started the practice of including trees in their farmlands for various purposes for various reasons, such as reducing risk from total crop failure, income generation, and distribution, and fulfilling different end uses. Most farmers will opt for a single tree that possesses multiple outputs if it is best for their farmlands. Such trees are generally known as Multipurpose trees (MPTs). More specifically, the term “multipurpose tree” refers to all woody perennials that are purposely grown to provide more than one significant contribution to the production or service functions (food, fodder, fuel, timber, shelter, shade and land sustainability) of the land use system they implement.

Desirable characteristics of MPTs

The general characteristics of the MPTs are climatic adaptability to a wide range of local conditions; fast growth; Indigenous; Ease of establishment from seeds and seedlings, Pest and disease resistance, inability to compete for moisture, space and air, ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen They provide multiple uses: food, feed, firewood, construction materials and other products and services. Minimal competition with agriculture crops, low crown diameter to bole diameter ratio with light branching pattern, straight bole, and good coppicing ability.

Major criteria that farmers must consider when selecting a species for various end uses Industrial uses (sawn timber, plywood, veneer, and pulpwood).

Criteria Characteristics of MPTs: Fast-growing (has a maximum growth rate in its early stage of development), Straight and uniform in size, Good natural pruning with rapid healing of wounds is advisable for

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producing sawn timber and plywood. For sawn timber: good physical and mechanical seasoning, preserving, and processing properties. For plywood and veneers, easy to peel, slice, and free of knots, For pulping: wood with a high density and preferably long fibres.

Suitable species: For sawn timber: *Tectona grandis*, For plywood and veneer: *Tectona grandis*, *Melia dubia*, *Dipterocarpus* spp, For pulpwood: *Eucalyptus* spp.

The details of types of wood, criteria/ characteristics of MPTs and suitable species are discussed as below:

1. Roundwood (*poles and posts*)

Criteria/Characteristics of MPTs: Fast growing, Straight bole, Produce few or thin branches. Self-pruning and without knots for strength, less taper, thin bark that strips easily, Durable wood Resist termite and wood borer infestations.

Suitable species: *Albizia lebbek* and *Casuarina equisetifolia*.

2. Fuelwood

Criteria/Characteristics of MPTs: It produces wood that splits easily, has a low moisture content, and dries quickly. When it burns, it produces low-toxicity smoke. Management should take as little time and effort as possible.

Suitable species: *Casuarina equisetifolia*, *Calliandra calothyrsus*, *Leucaena*

leucocephala, *Melia dubia*, *Gmelina arborea* and *Gliricidia sepium*.

3. Fodder

Criteria/Characteristics of MPTs: Fast-growing species, especially in early stages, are high in protein and nutrients, with highly palatable leaves and twigs that sprout well and withstand lopping, pruning, pollarding and coppicing.

Suitable species: *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, *Gliricidia sepium*, *Prosopis cineraria* and *Sesbania grandiflora*.

4. Windbreaks and shelterbelts

Criteria/Characteristics of MPTs: Fast-growing species with a small open crown will help reduce the risk of wind damage. Strong roots will be an important consideration and they must be easy to propagate also.

Suitable species: *Casuarina equisetifolia*.

5. Live fences

Criteria/Characteristics of MPTs: It grows quickly to a medium height and well in close spacing. Stiff branches, thorns, spines, nettles, or irritating latex will help to keep animals away. It must also be resistant to lopping and trimming and it must be kept in good condition.

Suitable species: *Cajanus cajan*, *Calliandra calothyrsus* and *Gliricidia sepium*.

6. Soil protection and rehabilitation

Criteria/Characteristics of MPTs: A tree with a spreading crown that grows quickly and has a vigorous root system to bind the soil and a strong taproot, especially in the areas prone to landslides, Nitrogen fixing ability is also an added advantage.

Suitable species: *Casuarina equisetifolia* and *Prosopis juliflora*.

7. Shade and nurse trees

Criteria/Characteristics of MPTs: A fast-growing evergreen tree with a dense crown is useful for providing shade to grazing animals as well as being simple to establish and maintain.

Suitable species: *Gliricidia sepium*, *Leucaena leucocephala* and *Sesbania grandiflora*.

Silviculture management of MPTs

Tree management practices are important for getting proper output from the agroforestry systems/ practices. It ensures better resource utilization, minimal interference between different components (tree, crop and livestock), sustainability in nutrient cycles, tree harvest and protection from internal and external stresses. The nature of the tree and the purpose for which it is grown are the main factors for deciding the kind of management practices.

Generally, tree management in agroforestry is classified into two i.e., Above

ground management practices and below-ground management practices. Some of these techniques are like those used in the management of trees in forestry plantations, but others are different. Thinning, lopping, pollarding, coppicing, bending, training and pruning are the most common above-ground tree management practices (Khanna, 1984; Chavan et al., 2017; and <http://ecoursesonline.iasri.res.in>).

1. **Thinning:** A felling made in an immature stand to improve the growth and form of trees that remain, without permanently breaking the canopy. It is done only to regulate the distribution of the growing space to improve the growth and form of the trees that are left.
2. **Lopping:** It is simply the cutting of tree branches, or more precisely, the removal of one-year shoots or fresh growth from the entire crown of the tree/plant to get sufficient fodder for livestock.
3. **Pollarding:** It is the practice of cutting a sapling or pole tree at some height above the ground level so that it produces new shoots from below the cut. It is generally done at a height of 2–2.5 m above ground level.
4. **Coppicing:** It is the cutting or heading back of the main stem at 20–30 cm from the ground level.

5. **Bending:** Restricting bole development to provide more food material to new leaf shoots. It is a very useful practice to produce a large quantity of foliage close to ground level.
6. **Training:** Vertically trained trees are desirable in agroforestry because they can avoid shade and light competition from underground crops, so training practice will help the

vertical spread of trees and ensure better growth of different components in the agroforestry system/practice.

7. **Pruning:** The removal of live or dead branches or multiple leaders from standing trees for the improvement of the tree or its timber.

Root pruning is the major below-ground tree management practice and it

Thinning

Lopping

Pollarding

Pruning

Root Pruning

(Source: <https://apps.worldagroforestry.org>)

is essential for reducing the nutrient and water competition between trees and crops. Trench and artificial root barriers are used for proper root management in agroforestry.

Agroforestry is one of the essential components in upholding the principle of sustainable development. Along with the environmental and social commitments, it focuses more on economic aspects like optimizing the production of food and wood and increasing the economic returns per unit area. To attain these objectives, various agroforestry models have been evolved and standardized. Various research organisations in our country are working more dedicatedly on the diagnosis of various agroforestry problems and the designing of more pragmatic and innovative models for different agroclimatic zones. Some of the major successful models

developed by ICAR Central Agroforestry Research Institute, Jhansi and in the All India Coordinated Research Project on Agroforestry (AICRPAF) are given in **Table 1**.

The significance of agroforestry is increasing day by day in meeting various socio-economic and environmental needs. Augmenting the production of food and wood is important for many developing countries like India because we are living in an uncertain world with the recurrent issues of poverty, pandemics, and other climatic setbacks (global warming, sea level rise, deforestation, degradation, etc). In this uncertain world, knowledge of the MPTs-based agroforestry systems and popularisation of their practices will solve most of the issues either directly or indirectly, along with our national and international commitments.

Table 1 – Successful agroforestry models of MPTs for South India (Handa et al., 2020)

Basic description of MPTs based agroforestry models						
Name of the Agroforestry model	Tree component	Suitable spacing	Rotation	Suitable Intercrops	Tree Productivity (Biomass)	Suitable States
Eucalyptus-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Eucalyptus tereticornis</i>	Block plantation (3m×3m or 4m×2m), Boundary Plantation (2-5 m)	For poles & pulpwood (3–4 years) and for plywood (6–8 years)	Kharif – Pearl millet, Cowpea, Sorghum, Soybean, Cotton. Rabi– Wheat, Potato, Barley, Oats, Berseem	260 t ha ⁻¹	Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu
Casuarina-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i>	Block plantation (1.5m×1.5m 2m×2m) Wind break (2m×1m) Agroforestry (4m×2m; 6m×2m)	For poles (2 years), for pulpwood (4-5 years) and for timber (8-12 years)	Kharif – groundnut, pulses, sesame. Rabi – vegetables; Perennial– banana	120-150 t ha ⁻¹ (Irrigated) & 70-100 t ha ⁻¹ (Rainfed)	Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Kerala
Melia-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Melia dubia</i>	Block plantation (3m×3m, 2.5m×2.5m) Boundary plantation (3-4m) Agroforestry (5m×5m, 6m×6m, 8m×2m)	For pulp (3-4 years) and for plywood (5-6 years)	Kharif – blackgram, cowpea, greengram, okra and groundnut; Rabi – sorghum, vegetable, ginger, turmeric, banana, papaya	148 t ha ⁻¹	Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Telangana and Andhra Pradesh

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Name of the Agroforestry model	Tree component	Suitable spacing	Rotation	Suitable Intercrops	Tree Productivity (Biomass)	Suitable States
Teak-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	Block plantation (2m×2m) Boundary plantation (2-5m) Agroforestry (8m×2m, 12m×2m)	20-25 years, intermediate yield from thinning at 7th & 12th year	Kharif – black gram, soybean, cotton, red gram and sesame. Rabi – sorghum, cowpea and linseed	1st thinning (50%) at 7th year (300 poles/ha) 2nd thinning (25%) at 12th year (Small timber 7.65 m ³ ha ⁻¹) Final harvesting (Timber: 77 m ³ ha ⁻¹)	Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana and Karnataka
Gamhar-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Timber (8m×2.5m, 6m×3m, 4m×3m) Pulp and small poles (1.2m×1.2m, 1.8m×1.8)	For small size timber (4-5 years) and for sawn timber (12-15 years)	Kharif – pulses and sesame Rabi – vegetable crops	200 t ha ⁻¹	Tamil Nadu and Kerala
Shisham-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i>	Boundary plantation (4-5m) Agroforestry (6m×4m, 8m×4m)	20-25 years	Kharif – paddy, soybean and pulses; Rabi – barley	148 t ha ⁻¹ (Firewood) and 20-25 m ³ ha ⁻¹ (Timber)	Tamil Nadu

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Name of the Agroforestry model	Tree component	Suitable spacing	Rotation	Suitable Intercrops	Tree Productivity (Biomass)	Suitable States
Ardu-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i>	Block plantation (3m×3m, 5m×5m) Boundary plantation (3m×3m) Agroforestry (10m×5m)	For match-splints (6-8 years) and for toys as well as sawn timber usage (15-20 years)	Kharif – pulses and legumes Rabi – barley	100-120 t ha ⁻¹ (Timber), 5-6 t ha ⁻¹ (Fodder) and 5-7 t ha ⁻¹ (Fuel wood)	Tamil Nadu
Kapok-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	Agroforestry (6m×6m and 8m×8m)	For light timber (20-25 years) For matchsticks (4-5 years) and starts producing floss after 3-4 years	Rainfed crops mainly pulses	Floss yield – 495 kg ha ⁻¹ from 9 years of plantation; Wood – 1-3 m per tree of a 70 cm diameter after 15 years	Rainfed regions of Tamil Nadu, Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka
Calliandra and Mulberry-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Calliandra calothyrsus</i> & <i>Morus alba</i>	Calliandra and Mulberry in the interspaces of Coconut at a close spacing of 45cm×45cm	15-years	Calliandra, Mulberry (11111 tree ha) and napier bajra hybrid is commonly grown at 3:2 ratio	Hybrid napier – bajra+ mulberry + Calliandra improved the productivity (31.5 tons dry matter ha ⁻¹)	Kerala, Tamil Nadu and parts of Karnataka

Basic description of MPTs based agroforestry models

Name of the Agroforestry model	Tree component	Suitable spacing	Rotation	Suitable Intercrops	Tree Productivity (Biomass)	Suitable States
Leucaena+ Gliricidia-based Agroforestry Model	<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> & <i>Gliricidia sepium</i>	3m×3m	15-20 years Stylo	Stylo (<i>Stylo santhes scabra</i>)	Leucaena – 9.20 t ha ⁻¹ Gliricidia – 18.5 t ha ⁻¹	Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Kerala

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